

Building Climate Resilience in Irish Forestry: A Review of Challenges and Strategies for Climate Adaptation

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Abstract

Irish forestry faces a convergence of ecological, policy, and legacy challenges that threaten its long-term sustainability and climate resilience. Historically shaped by afforestation policies favouring marginal land and dominated by a narrow range of fast-growing conifers, particularly Sitka spruce, the forest estate is highly vulnerable to windthrow, pest outbreaks, and emissions from peat-based soils. This review synthesises current evidence on abiotic and biotic stressors, including the implications of climate change, and evaluates a range of adaptive strategies to enhance resilience. These include species diversification, alternative silvicultural systems such as Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF), improved genetic material, Forest Assisted Migration (FAM) and the strategic use of harvested wood products in carbon reporting. The review also explores barriers to implementation, including fragmented governance, administrative frictions, and limited data on long-term forest performance. A landscape-level, pre-zoned approach is proposed to better match forest types to land suitability, improve ecosystem service provision, and streamline licensing systems. Supporting measures such as coordinated deer management, investment in long-term research infrastructure, and greater public sector involvement are highlighted as enablers of transformation. Ultimately, a shift toward a multifunctional, climate-resilient forest estate will require integrated planning, targeted financial incentives, and sustained collaboration across forestry, agriculture, biodiversity, and governance sectors.

Keywords: *adaptive capacity, proactive strategies, forest governance, forest health, climate change*

Introduction

Climate resilience encompasses the capacity to prepare for, recover from, and adapt to adverse climate-related events, while preventing the climate change impacts from worsening (Centre for Climate and Energy Solutions 2019). The concept of resilience has gained prominence in scientific literature and policy, particularly in response to accelerating climate change (Nikinmaa et al. 2020). It is difficult to define due to its application to a multitude of disciplines and systems. However, in the context of forestry, it refers to the capacity of an ecosystem to absorb disturbances, recover, and

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maintain core ecological, economic, and social functions (Holling 1973). Other climate adaptation concepts include resistance, the prevention of change and preservation of system stability; and transition, which assumes habitat change and necessitates active adaptation, including alterations to species composition (Palik et al. 2022).

Forest ecosystems are uniquely vulnerable to climate change due to their long lifespans and dependence on stable environmental conditions (Pawson et al. 2013). Ireland's forests face an uncertain future with risks from climate variability, including intensifying rainfall patterns, extended dry periods, rising temperatures and extreme weather events (Doran et al. 2019, Environmental Protection Agency 2015). Predictions indicate these threats could become more common, leading to greater uncertainty for forest health and productivity. Forestry plays a vital role in global (FAO & UNEP 2020) and national (Government of Ireland 2021; Government of Ireland 2023) climate change mitigation strategies, due to its carbon sequestration and storage potential. Between 2007 and 2016, Irish forests sequestered an average of 3.8 Mt CO₂ annually (COFORD 2020). Furthermore, from 2017 to 2022 the growing stock volume increased from 116.5 to 142 Mm³ (Jarman et al. 2024).

According to the fourth National Forest Inventory (NFI) (DAFM 2022), Ireland's forest resource spans c.800,000 ha, or 11.6% of the national land area, significantly below the EU average of 38% (DAFM 2022). Nearly 70% of the total forest area is comprised of plantations less than 30 years old, and the average age is 22 years. Overall, conifer species constitute the majority of the total forest area (64.1%), while broadleaf species (21.7%) and mixed forests (14.2%) comprise the remainder (ibid). Forestry contributes an estimated €2 billion annually to the Irish economy through timber production, wood manufacturing, and employment (Forestry Services Ltd. & Philips 2022).

Central to Irish forestry is Sitka spruce (*Picea sitchensis* (Bong.) Carr.), which dominates c. 50% of the forested area, primarily managed through rotation forest management (RFM), which involves clearfelling areas followed by replanting (DAFM 2022). It thrives in Ireland's currently highly favourable climatic conditions, and commercial rotations are routinely clearfelled within 30-40 years. It is common practice in Irish forestry for stands to be felled somewhat prematurely, before reaching maximum mean annual increment (MMAI), for example at MMAI minus c. 20% (Black et al. 2020). This is typically driven by the potential for higher economic returns (ibid), as well as concerns about windblow occurrence (Ní Dhubháin & Farrelly 2018; Dhubháin 1998). Sitka spruce's productivity allows for high carbon sequestration rates, with net ecosystem productivity (NEP) reaching 9 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, compared to a European conifer average of 6.5 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Black et al. 2009; Magnani et al. 2007). However, reliance on this individual species leaves Irish forestry highly vulnerable to climate-related stressors and ecological risks. Sitka spruce plantations are sensitive to changes in climatic conditions, pest outbreaks, and windthrow events (Tobin et al. 2018).

Irish forestry faces an unprecedented convergence of challenges including persistently low afforestation rates, legacy issues of peatland management, invasive species, over population of deer as well as climate change uncertainty, that threaten its ecological, economic and social sustainability. Building climate resilience is no longer optional but an urgent necessity. Achieving long-term climate goals requires a forest estate capable of withstanding climatic and ecological disturbances, while continuing to play a vital role in carbon capture, timber production and maintaining ecosystem service functions.

This review outlines the key challenges facing Ireland's forest resource, including legally binding climate targets, governance constraints, and both current and emerging abiotic and biotic threats. It evaluates a range of strategies to enhance resilience such as; species diversification, adaptive management, and alternative silvicultural approaches, while also considering the historical context and key barriers to implementation. Lastly, the review concludes with actionable recommendations to support the long-term sustainability of Irish forests.

Challenges facing Irish forestry

Climate targets and governance

Under the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021, Ireland has committed to achieving climate neutrality by 2050, with legally binding carbon budgets targeting a 51% reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2030 relative to 2018 levels (Casey & Carroll 2023). These national objectives align with Ireland's obligations under the Paris Agreement and the European Union's "Fit for 55" programme (Government of Ireland 2021). Failure to meet these targets could result in significant compliance penalties, potentially reaching c. €700 million per year in 2030 (Walker et al. 2023).

The Kyoto Protocol (KP) established a framework for using forests as tools to meet GHG targets, with detailed rules agreed in the Marrakesh Accords at COP 7 in 2001. The KP set 1990 as the baseline year, and only forests established since 1990 could be accounted as carbon sinks. Countries account for forest carbon stock changes across five pools, namely above and belowground biomass, litter, deadwood, and soil organic carbon. Article 3.3 of the KP focuses on afforestation, reforestation and deforestation, while Article 3.4 addresses forest management, including accounting for emissions from disturbances like fire and pests (IPCC, 2006; Black & Farrell 2006). Subsequent agreements, including the Paris Agreement at COP 21 in 2015, emphasized the conservation of forest carbon stocks and enhancement of sinks, with countries submitting nationally determined contributions (NDCs) every five years to limit global warming to the increasingly ambitious target of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels (IPCC 2023; Black et al. 2022). At EU level, the Land Use, Land

Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation, part of the “Fit for 55” targets, prioritises forest management over afforestation as a short-term mitigation strategy (EU 2022; Black et al. 2022).

In Ireland, the LULUCF sector has been a net source of GHG emissions from 1990 to 2019, unlike the rest of the EU, where it has generally been a net sink (Government of Ireland 2021). This discrepancy arises from GHG emissions (CO_2 , CH_4 , N_2O) from grasslands and wetlands outweighing sequestration by forests and harvested wood products (HWP). Unfortunately, this issue will worsen, with the forestry sector expected to shift from being a small remover of CO_2 (0.25 Mt CO_2 in 2021) to a net emitter (0.42 Mt CO_2 by 2025) (Jarman et al. 2024). This shift to net emissions represents a reversal of the forestry sector’s traditional role as a carbon sink and is especially unpalatable given the potential financial implications of missing emissions targets. According to Jarman et al. (2024), by 2030, overall net LULUCF emissions are projected to reach 7.1 Mt CO_2 eq. Should Ireland fail to meet its LULUCF commitments, the estimated cost of purchasing Land Removal Units (LRUs) compliance from other EU Member States could range between €0.5 and €5.8 billion, depending on the level of climate action taken and the market price of removal units (Irish Fiscal Advisory Council & Climate Change Advisory Council 2024).

The major factors contributing to this challenge are:

- I. The age structure of Ireland’s forests, with post 1990 forests (accountable under Kyoto Protocol framework) due for harvest in the coming years and associated emissions. Nearly 70% of the estate is less than 30 years old (DAFM 2022).
- II. Persistently low afforestation rates: the government’s target of 8,000 ha per year has only been achieved once between 2006 and 2024 (ibid) (Figure 1) and the proportion of land area under forestry remains low in comparison to the European average.
- III. Continued emissions from peatland forests, where the net soil carbon balance remains negative. Approximately 38% of existing Irish forests are planted on peat soils, with c.64% of this on deep peats (>90 cm) (Black et al. 2022; DAFM 2022).

A recent study confirmed that drained, afforested blanket peatlands in a maritime climate are net sources of soil CO_2 emissions (Jovani-Sancho et al. 2021). However, substantial uncertainty remains particularly around regional variation, peat type and depth, forest type, and carbon dynamics in second-rotation forests. Furthermore, additional studies are needed to identify optimal management practices for existing forests on peat soils, a crucial step in reducing LULUCF emissions.

To address these issues, the Climate Action Plan 2023 (Government of Ireland 2023) outlines strategies such as increasing afforestation rates, rehabilitating peatlands, and promoting sustainable forest management. Additional measures include reducing management intensity on grasslands over drained organic soils, improving carbon sequestration in grasslands on mineral soils and increasing the use of cover crops in tillage systems. However, progress toward these goals, especially in relation to afforestation, has fallen significantly short of national targets, casting serious doubt on Ireland’s ability to meet its legally binding climate commitments.

Abiotic disturbances

Abiotic damage, defined as damage to forest health considered to be an alteration of the normal growth pattern of the trees was recorded on 27% of the total forest area in the most recent NFI in 2022 (DAFM 2022). Abiotic damage can broadly be categorised into climatic variables and nutrient deficiency. While exposure related factors and nutrient deficiency are commonly associated with abiotic damage, they are not forms of damage in themselves but rather contributing factors. Exposure and nutrient deficiency are factors closely associated with site location and soil type. They affect c. 172,000 ha and c. 122,000 ha of forest respectively, with the majority of the damage severity being low to moderate. In turn, high and critical levels of damage severity affect c. 66,500 ha and are associated with severe impacts on tree growth and a likelihood of tree mortality in the near future.

Among various abiotic disturbances, this section focuses on windthrow and fire due to their present and potential impact. Windthrow represents one of the most significant

Figure 1: *Afforestation figures for Ireland between 2006-2024 (DAFM 2024a).*

threats to Irish forests (McInerney et al. 2016; Ní Dhubháin 1998), while fire, though currently of relatively low concern, may pose a more substantial risk in the future (Cardil et al. 2023). The extent of these disturbances is influenced by forest management decisions, which can either mitigate or exacerbate their effects, distinguishing them from site condition related damage.

Wind damage

Windthrow is a significant abiotic threat to Irish forests, dictated by Ireland's geographic location on the western edge of Europe, and exposure to Atlantic storms and cyclones (McInerney et al. 2016). High precipitation and the poor drainage status of many soils (especially blanket peats) contribute to shallow-rooted stands which are inherently vulnerable to wind damage (Mason 2015). Wind damage is categorized as endemic, caused by regular winter storms; or catastrophic, resulting from severe, infrequent events. Endemic windthrow affected 47,650 ha and catastrophic windthrow 8,010 ha of total forest area according to the NFI 2022 (DAFM 2022). An example of a catastrophic event was Storm Darwin which occurred in 2014, it caused widespread damage across nearly 8,000 ha of forests, exacerbated by saturated soils that reduced bearing capacity (McInerney et al. 2016). More recently, storm Éowyn caused extensive devastation in 2025 affecting c. 26,000 ha, over 40% of which occurred in Connaught (DAFM 2025a). Research highlights that gust speed, rather than mean wind speed, is the primary driver of tree failure, with site factors like drainage and stand height playing critical roles in determining susceptibility (Gallagher 2017; Brunet 2013). Management decisions aimed at mitigating windthrow often involve premature felling or avoidance of thinning (Ní Dhubháin & Farrelly 2018), both of which reduce timber yield and diminish the carbon sequestration potential of the national forest estate (Black et al. 2010). However, uncertainty remains regarding the full impact of these practices on total carbon balances, including carbon stored in HWP and long-term sequestration dynamics.

While thinning can promote the development of larger, wind-resistant trees over time, it temporarily increases windthrow risk, particularly on exposed sites (Mason 2015). On extremely exposed sites where windthrow risk is high, a “no-thin” management is often the best option for stability, mitigating the risk of wind penetration into the stand (Locatelli et al. 2016). Recent trends in forest management have suggested that a heterogeneous diverse canopy structure may offer more protection against wind damage than that of single-aged stands (Vitkova et al. 2013; Duperat et al. 2022; Pukkala et al. 2016). The creation of specially managed transition zones, such as planting mixed species at various spacings on the windward edge to allow wind to filter through has been suggested to reduce windthrow risk (Ní Dhubháin & Farrelly 2018). Other approaches include avoiding the removal of edge trees (Figure 2), timely or early thinning, specific non-commercial planting of stand boundaries, appropriate drainage and orienting planting lines to prevailing wind (ibid).

Figure 2: Storm damage post Storm Éowyn in Co. Sligo. Edge trees show greater wind firmness than those within the stand interior. Source Irish Farmers Journal and Western Forestry Co-op.

Species selection is also a key consideration in mitigating wind damage. Studies found that tree species with high wood density and slower radial growth, described as “conservative species”, exhibited greater resistance and resilience to wind events compared to fast-growing species (Barrere et al. 2024; Augusto et al. 2025). However, while fast-growing species were more vulnerable to wind damage, they demonstrated quicker recovery following storm events. Barrere et al (2024) also concluded that the dominant species within a stand had a greater influence on post-disturbance recovery than overall species diversity. It is important to note that despite some species’ greater resistance to wind, they are often less suited to challenging site conditions. In Ireland, forest wind damage is most likely on sites with poorly drained, nutrient-poor soils and at higher elevations with significant exposure, conditions that limit the suitability of many species for planting. Additionally, concerns that drainage can adversely affect water quality (DAFM 2018) can influence management decisions to reduce forest drainage intensity. Inadequate drainage can exacerbate shallow rooting behaviour in wet soils, increasing susceptibility to windthrow. Pre-emptive measures such as a well-designed, site-specific management plan that incorporates both broadleaf and conifer species (Barrere et al. 2024), along with the timely construction of roading (Ryan et al. 2005), have the potential to mitigate some of the risks associated with windthrow while maintaining forest productivity. However, uncertainties remain around how climate change will influence the timing, frequency, and intensity of future storm events (Noone et al. 2023).

Fire damage

Fire damage to Irish forests has been modest, with 7,260 ha of damage to the total forest area reported in the last NFI (DAFM 2022). However, while fire damage represents a relatively low risk, it is an emerging concern as climate change is expected to increase both the frequency and intensity of forest fires, mainly due to expected shifts in climate conditions, namely droughts (Galizia et al. 2023; Jones et al. 2022). Forest fires can lead to significant carbon emissions, biodiversity loss, economic damage, and, in severe cases, loss of human life. Recent trends in the occurrence of forest fires in northwestern Europe (Ireland, UK, Netherlands, Belgium), where fires were previously rare, highlight the growing threat (Cardil et al. 2023). The UK experienced record fire seasons in 2018 and 2019 with burned areas of c. 18,000 ha and c. 29,000 ha respectively (Belcher et al. 2021; Cardil et al. 2023). Similarly to Ireland, forest fires in the UK are frequently linked to prescribed burns for heathland management that escape control (DAFM 2021; Cardil et al. 2023). This is particularly relevant for Ireland, where peat soils cover approximately 23% of the total land surface and 38% of the forest estate, and are flammable under dry conditions (Gilet et al. 2024; DAFM 2022).

Fire risk in Ireland peaks in late winter and early spring, with drier vegetation in February to April being especially prone to ignition (Cardil et al. 2023), leading to Ireland's designated fire risk period from March to June (DAFM 2021). However, Ireland has limited experience of large-scale forest fires, and there is an associated lack of knowledge, infrastructure, and preparedness to manage such threats. The 2017 Cloosh Valley fire, which damaged 1,213 ha (828 ha of forest and 385 ha of non-forest peatland), serves as an example. The estimated cost of this event was approximately €3 million (Oireachtas 2019). During the same year, DAFM reported that up to 10,400 ha of open land, including 1,500 ha of forest land, was affected by fire (San-Miguel-Ayanz et al. 2018). Proactive fire management strategies, such as comprehensive fire plans and regularly maintained fire breaks have been shown to be effective methods for mitigating fire risk. This is critical in forested peatland areas, where carbon emission risks are highest.

Biotic disturbances

According to the most recent NFI, approximately 36% of the total forest area was affected by biotic damage, c. 22% of this area exhibited high or critical levels of damage and the remaining c.78% low to moderate levels of harm (DAFM 2022). The primary causes of biotic damage include – animal activity, particularly deer browsing (c. 105,000 ha), harvesting operations (c. 57,000 ha), disease (c. 47,000 ha) and insect (c. 8,000 ha).

Impact of deer

Deer damage, including browsing, fraying and bark stripping, presents a significant issue for Irish forestry. The three most commonly occurring species of deer are red deer

(*Cervus elaphus*), sika (*Cervus nippon*) and European fallow deer (*Dama dama*), while the muntjac deer (*Muntiacus reevesi*) is thought to have established a population as recently as the 2000s (Murphy et al. 2013; Höna et al. 2018). It is hard to quantify populations accurately, but the current assessment of distribution and abundance (Figure 3) highlights hotspot areas such as Wicklow and the South-West of the country (Morera-Pujol et al. 2023). While only the red deer species is native, all deer are protected species in Ireland under the Wildlife Act 1976. As a result, there are strict conditions regarding the time of year in which culling can occur and then only with a licence (Teagasc 2005).

Deer are widely recognized as a significant cause of economic damage in commercial forests (Purser et al. 2009). Broadleaf forests and native woodlands are particularly affected as deer are often the greatest constraint to establishment, development and subsequent management (Nugent 2012). This too is true for areas under management for Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF), a system which relies on natural regeneration. The absence of any natural predators for deer has allowed populations to increase unchecked with food availability and disease the primary limiting factors for populations (Höna et al. 2018). In the absence of a national deer management policy in Ireland, no definitive estimation of deer population distribution or density, and no single authority with jurisdiction over deer management (Purser et al. 2009), there are many gaps in the ability to control deer populations. Urgent action, as highlighted in previous reports (Purser et al. 2009; Murphy et al. 2013; Höna et al. 2018), is required to safeguard the conservation status of native woodlands, maintain wood quality in hardwood and conifer stands, and promote woodland regeneration to secure the long-term viability and resilience of the national forest resource.

Figure 3: Maps showing the distribution and relative abundance of the three main deer species in Ireland: a) red deer, b) sika deer, and c) fallow deer as predicted by Morera-Pujol et al. (2023). The values indicate relative abundances, with 0 reflecting absence of the species and values closer to 1 representing the areas where the species is more abundant. The pixel scale is $(5 \times 5 \text{ km})$.

Tree pathogens

Ash dieback (*Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*) is an ascomycete fungus which is causing a severe impact on native ash (*Fraxinus excelsior* L.) populations throughout Europe (Nemesio-Gorriz et al. 2019). The wind-dispersed spores infect leaves, the infection progresses into the shoots (causing crown dieback), and eventually into the bole of the tree before leading to mortality. The disease was first recorded in Ireland in 2012 on imported plant material and has since caused significant damage to both ash plantations and hedgerow trees, of which ash was a major component (McCracken et al. 2017). Overall, ash dieback is widespread in c. 34,000 ha of forests planted in Ireland (DAFM 2022). It is estimated that a proportion of the ash population (1-5%) will have a natural tolerance to *H. fraxineus* and there are ongoing efforts to breed for tolerance and create seed banks from which the population can be maintained (Plumb et al. 2020; Budde et al. 2016).

Phytophthora ramorum was first noted globally in the 1990s and well established in Europe and North America with its presence also noted in some Asian countries (Jung et al. 2021). It was first detected in Ireland in 2002 in *Rhododendron spp.* and in 2010 it was found to be infecting larch (*Larix spp.*), causing significant damage to commercial Japanese larch plantations (*Larix kaempferi* (Lamb.) Carr). It infected over c. 18,000 ha of larch in Ireland and the UK between 2010-2016 and has the potential to cause damage to European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.), specifically in the form of bleeding cankers (O’Hanlon et al. 2018). *P. ramorum* thrives in the cool, wet maritime climate of Ireland and sub-freezing temperatures for at least a week’s duration are necessary to eradicate the pathogen from infected leaf tissue (ibid).

Forest pests

The risk of damage to spruce forests by the green spruce aphid (*Elatobium abietinum*) is likely to increase under climate change. Feeding on spruce foliage, the aphid impairs growth and productivity, with trees on nutrient-poor or waterlogged sites being especially vulnerable (Day 2002). Aphid activity is strongly linked to temperature; mild winters enable their survival and reproduction, while temperatures below -7°C are needed to cause severe mortality (Banfield-Zanin & Leather 2015). High population densities of spruce aphid in 2002 led to significant loss of foliage, causing an 80–90% increase in litterfall during 2003–2004 (Tobin et al. 2006). While the 18–23% reduction in net ecosystem productivity in 2004 may have been compounded by drought and self-thinning after canopy closure, these findings underscore the potential impact of this pest, as well as the indirect effects of climate change on future forest productivity. Assessment of the true impact and extent of this pest on the national forest estate is hard to quantify accurately.

Similarly, the large pine weevil (*Hylobius abietis*), a major pest during replanting, presents another climate-driven challenge. Pine weevil feeds on the stem of young conifers, girdling them and causing significant mortality. Unprotected reforestation

sites in Ireland have reported seedling losses of up to 100% (DAFM 2022a). Currently this pest reproduces over a two-year life cycle, however, with climate change this is expected to shorten, potentially to one-year, allowing for faster population growth and increased damage (Stokes & Kerr 2009). If climate change leads to increased temperatures it is likely that both aphid and weevil infestations could worsen in severity and frequency. EU regulations under the Farm to Fork Strategy further complicate pest management by introducing non-legally binding pesticide reduction targets of 50% by 2030 (European Commission 2020). While laudable, these regulations necessitate alternative pest management approaches, such as Integrated Pest Management (IPM), which emphasizes non-chemical controls and the development of pest-resistant tree species. However, the transition to these methods requires significant changes to forest management practices and may, in the interim, increase vulnerability to pests like the pine weevil (DAFM 2022a).

Invasive plant species

Invasive species such as rhododendron (*Rhododendron ponticum*) and laurel (*Prunus laurocerasus*) pose additional challenges to Irish forestry. These species thrive in Ireland's climate, forming dense canopies that shade forest floors and prevent the regeneration of native species (both tree and herb), which is particularly evident in areas such as Killarney National Park (Cross 1981). The removal of these invasive species is labour-intensive and costly, yet without active management, the long-term viability of Ireland's remaining native woodlands is at serious risk, with severe consequences for biodiversity and ecosystem succession (Higgins 2008).

Climate change and uncertainty

Climate change is one of the biggest challenges facing humanity, mean global surface temperatures have increased by 1.1°C from 1850–1900 to 2011–2020 and are projected to increase by 1.4 to 4.4°C by 2100 (IPCC 2023). Ireland's climate is undergoing noticeable changes, with rising temperatures, increased rainfall, and more frequent extreme weather events (Walker et al. 2023). Over the past two decades, the annual average temperature has reached 10.2°C, an increase of 0.5°C compared to the previous 50-year average, with projections indicating it could rise to approximately 11°C by 2050 (Nolan & Flanagan 2020). Rainfall patterns are also shifting, with Ireland experiencing its wettest decade in 300 years, reflecting a long-term upward trend (Murphy et al. 2018). Seasonal variations in precipitation are becoming more pronounced, with significantly wetter winters and springs and drier summers (Domonkos et al. 2020).

Climate change not only amplifies existing risks but also increases the likelihood of new threats emerging within Ireland's forests. Many threats to the forest estate, both abiotic and biotic, are exacerbated by Ireland's reliance on Sitka spruce and

rotational forest management (RFM) (DAFM 2022). Variations in water availability are a key concern, studies found evidence that in years of drought stress (Black et al. 2010) or years of extreme precipitation events (Saunders et al. 2014) the forest carbon assimilation was negatively impacted. Ray et al. (2025) found that hot droughts and high summer temperatures are projected to become more frequent across much of Norway spruce's (*Picea abies* (L.) H. Karst) range, particularly as warming rises from +1 °C to +2 °C. These events reduce carbon uptake and growth by increasing evapotranspiration and water stress, leaving spruce more vulnerable to pest and disease outbreaks. At the same time, late-spring frosts remain a persistent risk, especially in Atlantic and Mediterranean regions where earlier budburst advances phenology into frost-prone windows. Such frosts can damage new foliage, depress photosynthesis, and delay leafing in the following year, further compounding productivity and resilience losses (ibid). As weather patterns become increasingly unpredictable, forests will need to adapt to shifting environmental conditions or risk losing functionality. However, the complexity and uncertainty surrounding future climate scenarios and their effects on forest growth raise concerns about species selection, current management practices (such as RFM) and the ability to mitigate the predicted challenges ahead.

Globalisation and international trade combined with climate change significantly increase the risk of pest and disease introductions to Ireland's forests (Jactel et al. 2023). Although Ireland benefits from EU Protected Zone status, which restricts the introduction of harmful organisms present elsewhere in Europe, previous outbreaks of *P. ramorum* and *H. fraxineus* (ash dieback) highlight the limitations of this protection. Rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns have the potential to create conditions favourable for the establishment and spread of invasive pests and diseases. Emerging threats, such as the great spruce bark beetle (*Dendroctonus micans*) and the European spruce bark beetle (*Ips typographus*), pose significant risks. Although not established in Ireland, these pests have developed populations in the UK, where *I. typographus* has demonstrated the capacity to attack both weakened and healthy trees when populations reach critical levels (Forestry Commission 2012; Tuffen & Grogan 2019; Teagasc 2023). These invasive species pose a high risk to forestry in Ireland if introduced, particularly as climate conditions become increasingly favourable for their survival and reproduction. While Ireland's Protected Zone legislation aims to prevent the introduction of harmful pests and diseases, the combination of global trade and changing climatic conditions increases the likelihood of new threats establishing themselves.

In the face of these uncertainties the implementation of proactive strategies to enhance forest resilience is required. The vulnerabilities within Ireland's forest estate to both existing and emerging threats are evident, highlighting the need for anticipatory rather than reactionary measures.

Strategies for enhancing forest climate resilience

Building climate resilience in Irish forestry requires an integrated approach that addresses economic, ecological, and social dimensions across multiple spatial and temporal scales. This includes coordinated action from individual forest stands to national-level policy. At the national scale, the resilience of the forest sector is constrained by its heavy reliance on Sitka spruce and RFM, which, while economically important, leaves the sector vulnerable to both climatic and ecological threats. Therefore, national-level strategies must include diversifying forest composition, support for genetic adaptation and assisted migration efforts, as well as development of a robust national deer management strategy. These efforts can be enabled through mechanisms such as the Forestry Programme 2023–2027¹, which provides grant incentives for forest types that contain species diversity and promote alternative management practices. At the stand level, forest resilience can be enhanced through site-specific decisions on management systems, including the adoption of alternative silvicultural approaches such as Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF), as well as diverse planting schemes. By combining local and national strategies, Irish forestry can shift from reactive management toward a proactive, climate-adaptive system capable of withstanding future challenges.

Diversifying forest composition

Diversifying forest composition is a fundamental strategy for enhancing the climate resilience and sustainability of Irish forestry. Mixed-species plantations have demonstrated the ability to be more productive and resilient than monocultures, making better use of resources such as light, water, and nutrients (Hulvey et al. 2013; Kambach et al. 2019). These benefits stem from complementary growth patterns, such as pairing fast-growing, light-demanding species with slower-growing, shade-tolerant species optimising resource use and enhancing overall productivity (Depauw et al. 2024). Furthermore, diverse forests are less susceptible to disturbances like pests and extreme weather events (Jactel et al. 2017; Liu et al. 2022) with recent evidence showing that mixtures of tree species with diverse mycorrhizal associations can also enhance drought resistance and resilience (Sachsenmaier et al. 2024).

Examples of species mixtures trialled in Ireland:

- Norway spruce and birch (*Betula spp.*): Birch provides frost protection and soil enrichment through its leaf litter, supporting spruce development on challenging sites (Black et al. 2017).
- Oak (*Quercus spp.*) with alder (*Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn.) or birch: These mixtures achieve higher productivity in Irish conditions, particularly in nutrient-poor sites, by leveraging the fast growth of alder or birch (Renou-Wilson et al. 2008).

¹ www.gov.ie/en/department-of-agriculture-food-and-the-marine/publications/forestry-grants-and-schemes/#forestry-programme-2023-2027

- Sitka spruce and lodgepole pine (*Pinus contorta* Douglas ex Loudon): This combination benefits from self-thinning dynamics, where spruce eventually dominates without sacrificing early productivity (Horgan et al. 2004).

Despite advantages, there are barriers to widespread adoption of mixed-species plantations in Ireland. A lack of practical experience in managing mixed stands and difficulties in modelling timber yield for diverse systems pose challenges (Keane et al. 2018; Pretzsch et al. 2015). Economic considerations must also be considered, as mixed plantations often require higher management costs, specialized machinery, and skilled personnel (Depauw et al. 2024). Furthermore, site conditions such as soil type, exposure, and altitude influence the success of mixed plantations, as with any forest establishment. Research indicates that mixed-species plantations perform better on marginal or less fertile sites, while monocultures may outperform them on high-quality land (Toigo et al. 2015). For example, in British upland conditions, oak was found to grow better in mixture with Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) or alder than in monoculture, highlighting the benefits of using complementary species to improve performance on exposed, challenging sites (Leslie & Short 2025).

Another challenge lies in identifying optimal species mixtures for Irish conditions. While the new Forestry Programme 2023–2027 promotes mixed high forests with at least 20% broadleaves (DAFM 2024b), knowledge gaps persist regarding useful combinations of species, their management, and their compatibility with future climate scenarios. Evidence demonstrates that species compatibility depends not only on traits like shade tolerance and growth rate, but also on planting configuration, such as intimate and non-intimate mixtures, band designs etc. (Leslie & Short 2025). Intimate mixtures require careful matching of growth characteristics and regular interventions to maintain balance, whereas band planting, using blocks of at least three rows, can reduce interspecific competition and provide a more robust structure under variable management (ibid). These practical insights highlight the need for locally adapted silvicultural guidance to foster successful implementation. For example, trials such as the Kronoberg approach, which utilizes birch and Norway spruce combinations, have shown an increase in productivity on peat sites but remain underexplored on alternative soils and site conditions in Ireland (Black et al. 2020). Similarly, mixed plantations involving oak and alder or birch demonstrate potential but require further research to optimise management practices (Renou-Wilson et al. 2008). Careful planning of planting densities and thinning schedules is crucial to maintaining the balance between competition and growth in mixed plantations (Ratcliffe et al. 2017). Effective diversification strategies must be conscious of commercial viability and adaptability to climate change to guide species selection and management.

On an individual forest or stand scale, where the average size of private grant-aided afforestation between 1980 and 2023 was 8.5 ha (DAFM 2024a), economic barriers to species diversification exist. The unparalleled productivity of Sitka spruce in Irish conditions, combined with its tolerance of poor site conditions and a well-established timber market, makes it highly suitable for commercial forestry. However, at national scale, reducing reliance on Sitka spruce is crucial to enhancing the climate resilience of Irish forestry. This can be achieved through targeted incentives to encourage the establishment of alternative species. Walsh et al. (2017) investigated potential substitutes for larch following the outbreak of *P. ramorum* in Ireland. The study identified several alternative conifer species with promising potential when planted on suitable sites:

- Norway spruce
- Western red cedar (*Thuja plicata* Donn ex D.Don)
- Western hemlock (*Tsuga heterophylla* (Raf.) Sarg.)
- Grand fir (*Abies grandis* (Douglas ex D.Don) Lindl.)
- Noble fir (*Abies procera* Rehder)
- European silver fir (*Abies alba* Mill.)
- Douglas fir (*Pseudotsuga menziesii* (Mirb.) Franco)
- Coastal redwood (*Sequoia sempervirens* (D.Don) Endl.)

Integrating Sitka spruce, native to the west coast of North America, with other Pacific Northwest species such as Douglas fir, Grand fir, Western hemlock, and Western red cedar offers an opportunity to enhance resilience while maintaining productivity. However, further research is needed to assess the economics of such an approach, long-term viability and best management of such combinations in Irish conditions (Walsh et al. 2017).

Diversifying forest composition offers a pathway to enhance the climate resilience, productivity, and ecological value of Irish forestry. By incorporating mixed-species plantations tailored to site-specific and future climate projections, Ireland can reduce its reliance on Sitka spruce and better prepare for anticipated threats. However, achieving these outcomes will require overcoming significant economic and operational barriers. Success will depend on robust research to optimise species-site matching and planting design, policy alignment to provide financial and regulatory support, and active stakeholder engagement to ensure practical implementation and long-term sustainability.

Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF)

Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF) is a close-to-nature silvicultural approach that maintains a continuous forest canopy through partial harvesting and natural regeneration (Wilson et al. 2018). By encouraging irregular stand structure with diverse species composition and age classes, CCF provides a robust framework for building climate

resilience in Irish forests, particularly in the face of climate change and ecological disturbances (Mason 2015). In contrast to conventional RFM, CCF reduces the risk of pest outbreaks, such as pine weevil, which thrives on large, open clearfelled areas, by avoiding conditions that favour sudden population build-up (Pitkänen et al. 2008). Timber is harvested more consistently, across a range of assortments, and replanting costs are lower due to reliance on natural regeneration, which can be supplemented where needed (Ní Dhubháin 2003; Spazzi et al. 2019). Beyond operational and resilience benefits, continuous cover systems also provide broader multifunctionality. Peura et al. (2018) found that CCF delivered higher net present value for timber, greater carbon sequestration, improved scenic value, and enhanced habitat availability compared to rotation forestry in Finland. These findings suggest that CCF can simultaneously support production and conservation objectives, aligning with Irish forestry's evolving multifunctional role.

Windthrow resilience under CCF remains a subject of debate. From one perspective, its irregular structure and continuous canopy may reduce susceptibility compared to even-aged RFM (Pukkala et al. 2016). In contrast, Potterf et al. (2022) suggests that taller trees and frequent thinning can increase wind damage risk. Further, Savill et al. (1997) argued that conifer-broadleaf mixtures might be more susceptible to storm damage due to the turbulence in the stand caused by open pockets of leafless deciduous trees during storm-prone times. Importantly, CCF has been shown to reduce volume at risk, due to lower standing timber volumes at any given time (Potterf et al. 2024). Overall, consideration of site-specific factors such as soil type, elevation and exposure along with management decisions relating to thinning timing and intensity are critical for effective management of windblow, for which there are knowledge gaps relating to Irish conditions.

The carbon dynamics of CCF versus RFM remain underexplored, complex and context-dependent. Modelling exercises suggest that CCF could sequester up to 100 t CO₂ more per hectare over a 100-year period compared to RFM, due to ongoing biomass accumulation and reduced site disturbance (FERS, n.d.). However, this benefit may be offset by wind damage risk associated with taller trees and more frequent interventions (Potterf et al. 2022). In high-yielding stands, such as those with Sitka spruce, RFM optimised for maximum mean annual increment (MMAI) may achieve higher sequestration rates by exploiting the high growth associated with early phases of stand development (Carlisle et al. 2023). Recent evidence suggests that an increasing proportion of Irish Sitka spruce stands are capable of exceeding Yield Class 26 (Dowd & Nieuwenhuis 2024). While questions remain regarding soil carbon balance in CCF systems, Roth et al. (2023) indicate a higher potential for future carbon accumulation under CCF compared to RFM. Ultimately the overall carbon balance of any system depends not only on forest growth and soil processes, but also on the end use of harvested

biomass, whether it results in long-lived wood products or short-term carbon emissions (Lundmark et al. 2016; Nave et al. 2024).

Despite its benefits, CCF adoption in Ireland remains limited, representing only around 1% of the forested area (Spazzi et al. 2019). Barriers include regeneration failure due to high deer populations (Vitkova et al. 2013), limited yield modelling for irregular stands, and a sawmilling sector oriented toward uniform timber assortments (Leslie et al. 2024). A significant barrier is access to skilled practitioners and educational programmes on how to manage CCF stands. However, initiatives such as Pro Silva Ireland² along with demonstration sites and field trials, are helping build practitioner experience and evidence for CCF's feasibility and multiple benefits under Irish conditions (Wilson et al. 2018). CCF presents a flexible and climate-resilient management model capable of delivering multiple ecosystem services, Peura et al. (2018) suggests that CCF can serve as a viable compromise, balancing timber production with ecological integrity. However, realising the full potential will require a nationally coordinated deer management strategy, strengthened education programmes, expanded growth and yield and species suitability research, as well as a clearer understanding of carbon dynamics. As Vitkova et al. (2013) note, resistance to new silvicultural models is to be expected, but long-term adoption will depend on sustained investment in knowledge sharing, demonstration, and policy support.

Forest Assisted Migration (FAM) and genetic adaptation

Forest Assisted Migration (FAM) is gaining recognition as a crucial tool for aiding forests adapt to climate change. It has been suggested as a method to address the predicted large-scale redistribution of tree species and the potential decline in species diversity (Aitken et al. 2008; Malcolm et al. 2002). It involves introducing tree genotypes and species better suited to future climatic conditions to maintain productivity and ecosystem services (Palik et al. 2022). While FAM is considered a novel approach, provenance selection, a core component of forest management, has been practiced for decades to maximise productivity and minimise environmental stress. Provenance selection is not explicitly considered FAM, however, there are similarities between the two approaches. Provenance selection focuses on the maximisation of forest functionality, while FAM focuses on ensuring forest function given climate change. An example, Sitka spruce, native to North America, planted in Ireland was originally sourced from Haida Gwaii, formerly referred to as Queen Charlotte Islands (QCI) provenance. However, provenance trials revealed that material from Washington and Oregon offered significantly better yields (Thompson et al. 2005) and have been used exclusively since 2006 (Thompson 2007).

Climate projections emphasise the importance of such efforts. Although not specific to Irish conditions, it is predicted that Sitka spruce in the south-west of England will

² <https://prosilvairland.com/>

experience reductions in productivity in the order of $10 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$ by the 2080s (Moffat et al. 2012). Therefore, provenance selection can prove a vital tool in establishing material best suited to future climate. Stokes et al. (2018) investigated hybridisation between Sitka spruce and white spruce (*Picea glauca* (Moench) Voss.) in the UK. Results indicated that the hybrid matched the productivity of Haida Gwaii Sitka spruce. These species, which hybridise naturally, were chosen to find a hybrid which is more drought tolerant yet retains the desirable characteristics of Sitka spruce (Leslie et al. 2024). An example of FAM can be found in British Columbia, Canada, where seeds are sourced from regions that already experience climatic conditions similar to those anticipated in the future (O’Neill et al. 2017). For Ireland, where longer summer droughts, increased winter rainfall, and an extension of the growing season by 35–40 days are anticipated by mid-century (Environmental Protection Agency 2015), selecting suitable species and provenances will prove critical in ensuring climate resilience and maintaining the functionality of Irish forests into the future.

FAM holds significant potential in Ireland. With only 28 native tree species, of which just three are conifers and only one is suitable for timber production, relying solely on native species is untenable for meeting future forestry demands under changing climate conditions (Leslie et al. 2024). While the principle of using local genetic material remains relevant and holds value, it should be interpreted in a broader sense, focusing on climatic similarity rather than geographic proximity (Alía et al. 2022). This shift supports the use of assisted migration to align seed sources with future site conditions, allowing seed deployment zones to move beyond traditional collection boundaries. A pragmatic approach to FAM would involve sourcing provenances of native species from more southerly regions of their indigenous range. For example, oak provenances might be sourced from northwest France or the Netherlands, which may be better adapted to future Irish conditions (COFORD 2020). In fact, the Climate Matching³ tool shows Ireland’s projected climate for 2051–2079 is the same as what is currently experienced in regions in the Netherlands, western France and northern Spain. Similarly, expanding the portfolio of non-native species could reduce vulnerability to climate-related risks while increasing productivity. Several species have shown potential in Irish conditions (Black et al. 2010; COFORD 2020), namely:

- Douglas fir
- Southern beech (*Nothofagus nervosa* (Phil.) Krasser)
- Monterey pine (*Pinus radiata* D. Don)
- Maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster* Aiton)
- Beech
- Hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus* L.)
- Sycamore (*Acer pseudoplatanus* L.)
- Spanish chestnut (*Castanea sativa* Mill.)

³ <https://climatematch.org.uk/>

Despite this, FAM is not without challenges. Concerns include potential maladaptation of genetic material to local environments and a lack of expertise and infrastructure for such efforts. Furthermore, there is a “social license” issue, as public and policy acceptance of introducing non-native or modified species is not guaranteed (Neff & Larson 2014; Palik et al. 2022).

Recent advances in tree breeding are reshaping strategies for assisted migration and genetic adaptation in European forestry. For example, the B4EST project demonstrated how high-resolution climate projections, genomic tools, and reaction norm models can be used to identify provenances and genotypes with adaptive traits including drought tolerance, pest resistance, and phenotypic plasticity (Ray et al. 2022). By integrating this knowledge into seed orchard programmes and forest reproductive material deployment, forest managers can select material with both high adaptive potential and economic value. Such approaches enhance the role of assisted migration from being primarily species-level translocation to also incorporating intra-specific genetic diversity and functional traits, thereby reducing risks of maladaptation under climate extremes (ibid).

Genetic adaptation through breeding programs can also play a critical role in ensuring the climate resilience of Irish forests. The Irish Sitka Spruce Tree Improvement Programme (ISSTIP) has operated since the 1970s, leveraging international trials such as those established by IUFRO in 1975 (Thompson 2013). This program has produced genetically improved Sitka spruce with higher yields and improved timber quality, contributing to carbon capture and long-term storage in HWP (COFORD 2020). Recent genetic studies have identified significant gene flow within Sitka spruce populations in North America, which could help identify traits like pest resistance (Byrne et al. 2022). Maintaining genetic diversity is essential for ensuring resilience against emerging pests and diseases, as demonstrated by ash populations affected by ash dieback, where those with higher genetic variation showed greater resistance (McKinney et al. 2014; Budde et al. 2016).

The lessons from ash dieback illustrate the importance of balancing genetic improvement with the preservation of diversity. Breeding for productivity should avoid creating genetically uniform populations, which could leave forests more vulnerable to unforeseen challenges. Instead, integrating FAM with robust genetic improvement programs offers a path to fostering climate resilience, ensuring that Irish forestry can adapt to the uncertainties of climate change while maintaining its economic, ecological and social viability.

Barriers to implementing climate resilience strategies

Efforts to enhance climate resilience in Irish forestry face multiple barriers across economic, governance, and knowledge systems. These challenges stem from the legacy of previous practices, fragmented governance frameworks, and a lack of long-term research and data. Addressing them is essential to meeting Ireland’s afforestation, biodiversity and climate

commitments, such as those outlined in the Climate Action Plan (2023), the Forestry Strategy to 2030, the EU Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission 2020), and the Nature Restoration Law (European Commission & Council 2024). However, overcoming these barriers requires a nuanced understanding of the interrelated issues.

Legacy, economics and ownership

Ireland's current forest composition and afforestation patterns are deeply shaped by historical policy decisions, economic realities, and land ownership structures. Understanding these structural and legacy factors is essential to contextualise the challenges currently facing efforts to diversify species, enhance climate resilience, and meet national afforestation targets.

To understand the historic distribution of forestry in Ireland, governmental policy was such that afforestation was only to occur when there was no agricultural use for the land (Farrelly et al. 2009). As a result, most afforestation was confined to marginal or sub-marginal agricultural land. One consequence of this policy was that, from the early 1950s until the mid to late 1980s, considerable areas of marginal land (i.e. unsuitable for agriculture) were afforested, particularly in regions such as Cloosh Valley in Galway and the blanket peat areas of south-west Sligo and north-west Mayo. These areas were planted mainly with Sitka spruce and lodgepole pine (O'Grainneil 1956; Condon 1961). The legacy of these past policies and practices is clearly reflected in the current forest estate, as c. 38% of forests are planted on peat soils, c. 64% of which are on deep peats (DAFM 2022). These practices are now widely recognised as detrimental to both biodiversity and carbon outcomes (Jovani-Sancho et al. 2021; Sloan et al. 2024; Jurasinski et al. 2024) and significant questions remain regarding the most appropriate and feasible management of these sites.

Significant economic barriers hinder the diversification of Ireland's national forest estate, some of which relate to ownership patterns. The national estate can be broadly divided into three separate categories (Table 1). Coillte, a semi-state company, was established in 1988 under the Forestry Act with a commercial mandate to operate profitably. Since 2003, Coillte has been ineligible for government grant aid, which has shifted the primary responsibility for afforestation from the state to private landowners, albeit with government funded grant-aid. Notably, 82% of the area afforested since 1980 has been established by farmers (DAFM 2024a). Despite efforts under the Forestry Programme 2023-2027 to make alternative forest types financially attractive, economic realities heavily favour Sitka spruce. Its rapid growth, tolerance of challenging site conditions, and established timber market have made it the most economically viable choice for landowners. Sitka spruce can achieve profitable rotations within 30–40 years, while native broadleaf species such as oak may require up to 120 years (Marques et al. 2024) and will likely require fencing protection against deer browsing. Alternative conifer

species also face challenges, often growing more slowly, being more site demanding, and lacking the same level of market demand as Sitka spruce.

Species selection patterns under the previous Forestry Programme 2004–2023 also illustrate commercial preferences. Grant categories dominated by Sitka spruce (i.e. GPC 1 - Unenclosed Sitka spruce/lodgepole pine, GPC 2 - Sitka spruce/lodgepole pine, and GPC 3 - Diverse mix with 10–20% of other species) accounted for c. 66% of total planting during this period. In contrast, alternative conifers (GPC 4) represented just 9%, while broadleaf categories (GPC 5–12, including agroforestry) comprised 24% (DAFM 2024a). This distribution reflects a persistent preference for commercial species, particularly Sitka spruce. Key stakeholders, such as Coillte (up to 2003) and farmers (post 1980), have been instrumental in driving afforestation in Ireland. However, this has led to a position in which forest composition consists of 50.5% Sitka spruce, while also accounting for 78.5% of the annual standing volume felled (DAFM 2022). The new Forestry Programme 2023–2027 has significantly increased premiums, making afforestation more profitable than many existing land uses (Duesberg et al. 2014). However, uptake remains limited with just c. 1,600 hectares planted in 2023 (DAFM 2024a).

Understanding the historical context, ownership structures, and economic realities is essential before meaningful steps can be taken to enhance the long-term climate resilience and functionality of the forest estate. These structural conditions, shaped over decades by policy decisions and economic pragmatism, have not only reinforced dependence on a narrow range of species but have also set the stage for the implementation challenges that now follow.

Table 1: *Ownership categories, average forest property size and proportion of Ireland's national estate, with a brief description (DAFM 2022).*

Category	Proportion of National Estate	Proportion planted in Sitka spruce	Average size	Description
Public	49.1%	57.9%	73 ha	All State-owned forests, mainly Coillte
Private (grant-aided)	35.7%	60.8%	8.6 ha	Private afforested land which was in receipt of either grant and/or premium since 1980
Private (non-grant aided)	15.2%	5.7%	NA	Private forests not in receipt of grant-aid post 1980. Includes areas of semi-natural forests that have regenerated naturally and other long-standing plantations on private estate holdings

Governance

Ireland's national target to expand productive forest cover to 18% by 2046 originally required an afforestation rate of 8,000 hectares per year (Farrelly & Gallagher 2015). However, this target was achieved only once between 2006 and 2024, and as a result, the revised figure needed to meet 18% land cover by 2050, alongside associated climate targets, has now risen to an estimated 18,000 hectares per year (O'Donoghue 2022).

“Administrative frictions”, as highlighted by Lentz et al. (2024), are a key barrier to afforestation in Ireland. These include complex procedures for land classification, long and unpredictable approval timelines, and burdensome requirements such as “Further Information Required” letters, which contribute to delays and uncertainty. Additional environmental compliance obligations under the Forestry Programme 2023–2027 have added to the administrative load. Fragmented licensing requirements, covering separate approvals for afforestation, roading, thinning and felling, combined with inconsistent decision-making and poor inter-agency communication, continue to undermine confidence among landowners, particularly smaller-scale actors (Lentz et al. 2024). The legacy of ash dieback has also likely contributed to hesitancy around forestry as a long-term land-use choice. These challenges highlight the urgent need to streamline administrative processes, increase transparency and strengthen stakeholder engagement. Persistently low afforestation rates, despite the rollout of the new programme, reflect ongoing systematic challenges within the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine. Without decisive efforts to reduce these bureaucratic barriers, or reconsider the need for individual licensing of operations, the financial cost of missing LULUCF targets will continue to escalate (Irish Fiscal Advisory Council & Climate Change Advisory Council 2024).

Lessons from other European countries highlight the potential for more streamlined approaches. In Sweden, a notably different governance model is in place. Under the 1993 Forest Policy and Forest Act, Sweden introduced the principle of “freedom with responsibility”, granting forest owners greater autonomy while ensuring compliance with sustainability goals (Roberge et al. 2020). Unlike Ireland's fragmented system, Sweden does not require individual licences for most forestry operations. Instead, landowners operate under a national framework of guidelines and best practices, which “aimed to grant forest owners more autonomy while ensuring sustainable forest management” (Future of Forestry 2024). This streamlined model reduces administrative burdens and promotes proactive engagement, particularly among Sweden's 313,000 individual forest owners, who collectively manage over half of the country's productive forest land (ibid). This model illustrates how simplifying procedures and placing trust in forest owners can help unlock afforestation potential while maintaining environmental safeguards.

A related challenge, identified by Pecurul-Botines et al. (2023), concerns the perceived marginalisation of forest owners in policy processes. In Ireland, as in Germany, Italy,

and Lithuania, landowners are often viewed as having less influence in national forestry decision-making than other interest groups. In particular, “environmentalist voices” are seen as more influential in shaping policy agendas and regulatory frameworks. This perceived imbalance may contribute to disengagement among private landowners and hinder wider adoption of sustainable forest management and afforestation.

Alongside administrative issues, inaction on implementing a national deer management strategy continues to hinder climate resilience efforts in Ireland. Deer browsing pressure poses a serious threat to the successful expansion of native woodland and the adoption of Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF) practices, both of which are key to enhancing carbon storage and fulfilling EU biodiversity restoration targets. Currently, all four deer species in Ireland are protected under the Wildlife Act of 1976 (Höna et al. 2018), yet there is no single responsible body or national framework guiding deer population control. In contrast, Scotland offers a more structured and strategic model. Scottish Natural Heritage (now NatureScot) is mandated under the Deer (Scotland) Act 1996 to lead on deer management and regularly assess national compliance with the Code of Practice on Deer Management (Granville & Hunter 2019). This framework outlines clear responsibilities for landowners and promotes sustainable management practices across themes including deer welfare, environmental protection, and sustainable economic development. Such a coordinated approach is crucial to meeting ambitious climate and biodiversity goals under the EU Nature Restoration Law, which mandates the restoration of at least 20% of the EU’s land and sea areas by 2030, rising to 60% by 2040 and 90% by 2050 (European Commission & Council 2024).

Knowledge gaps and role of research

Effective forest policy and planning require a solid evidence base. Yet in Ireland, critical knowledge gaps persist across spatial and temporal scales, undermining the sector’s capacity to respond to climate challenges. A lack of long-term and strategic research specific to Irish conditions is a key barrier to implementing climate resilience strategies. Knowledge gaps manifest differently across stand, regional, and national scales, particularly in how forestry may interact or integrate with other land uses, emphasizing the need for tailored solutions. Research has the potential to reduce resistance to change amongst stakeholders and improve the public perception of forestry. It is also crucial for assessing FAM methods and species suitability, however, addressing these challenges requires long-term, sustained investment in forest research.

Research funding is generally limited to projects of two to four years duration and “is in itself not sufficient” (COFORD 2020). While this specific critique relates directly to forest breeding programmes, similar shortcomings affect other aspects of forestry research. For example, a review conducted by Keane et al. (2018) identified 18 field trials containing mixed species, however, no work had been carried out on those trials

since 2013 and “it is highly likely they have fallen into disrepair or were harvested as part of surrounding stands”. This represents a significant missed opportunity to evaluate species compatibility, growth dynamics, and resilience under mixed-species systems. Forestry, by nature, is a long-term land use that requires long-term monitoring, before yielding meaningful results. Without long-term data collection, critical questions about alternative species, species mixtures, climate impacts on growth, and carbon dynamics remain unanswered. Black et al. (2010) opined that to quantify and characterise impacts of climate change on forest productivity would require process-based modelling. Yet such model systems rely on robust, long-term region-specific datasets for which there is little data in an Irish context. Alternatively, adapting NFI protocols, conducted on a five-year cycle, could provide a valuable opportunity to gather long-term growth and yield data. The lack of long-term monitoring plots in Ireland risks leaving the sector reliant on extrapolated data from other regions, which may not align with local conditions. The establishment and continued maintenance of “test sites” has the potential to serve dual purposes: (1) as research hubs for evaluating climate resilience-focused strategies, and (2) as demonstration forests to build stakeholder confidence and disseminate educational and practical management guidelines.

At stand level, knowledge gaps often relate to site-specific factors, such as optimal species-site matching, impacts of silvicultural practices, and deer browsing damage. At regional level, challenges arise from Ireland’s diverse environmental conditions, requiring localised research to inform climate-adaptive management. At national level, the absence of integrated long-term monitoring undermines the ability to plan strategically for climate resilience, carbon sequestration and biodiversity goals. In summary, investment in long-term, scale-sensitive research is a strategic necessity (FAO 2020; Pecurul-Botines et al. 2023). Without this commitment, Ireland risks falling behind in meeting its climate and biodiversity targets, while also forfeiting the long-term economic, ecological and social benefits of a climate-resilient forest estate.

Discussion

Irish forestry faces an unprecedented convergence of challenges that undermine its capacity to build climate resilience (Figure 4). A combination of governance issues, biotic and abiotic pressures, and key knowledge gaps has left the sector in a precarious position and highly vulnerable.

One of the most pressing concerns is the sector’s role as a net carbon source (Jarman et al. 2024). The consequences of past inaction on afforestation (Figure 1) are now becoming visible in what has been termed a “carbon cliff” (Climate Change Advisory Council 2023), a steep decline in carbon sequestration capacity, which comes at a time of rising compliance costs under EU-level climate targets (Irish Fiscal Advisory Council & Climate Change Advisory Council 2024). Looking ahead, the age structure

of Ireland's forests adds complexity to the supply of timber volume into the future. Some 70% of Ireland's forest area consists of plantations under 30 years old, with an average age of just 22 years (DAFM 2022). Many of these forests are due to be clearfelled in the coming decade, temporarily boosting domestic supply, with a peak of 7.9 million m³ projected in 2035 (COFORD 2022). However, this short-term increase will be followed by a sharp decline in available volume. A structural issue rooted in the age class imbalance of the existing forests estate. Even with a dramatic increase in the current rate of afforestation, this supply gap is now unavoidable due to the growth timelines of newly planted forests. At the same time, Ireland's Protected Zone Status under EU biosecurity rules limits the ability to offset supply deficits through imports, in order to prevent the introduction of harmful beetle species present elsewhere in Europe (DAFM 2020). Together, these intersecting pressures, declining domestic supply and limited import capacity, pose a significant threat to the long-term viability of the forestry sector. In particular, they jeopardise the future of Ireland's timber processing industry and the stability of domestic timber markets.

Meeting these challenges will require a shift in thinking and approach. As Albert Einstein noted, "We cannot solve our problems with the same thinking we used when we created them." In this context, it is clear that incremental changes will not be sufficient. While efforts are already underway to diversify planting through the Forestry Programme 2023–2027, progress has been limited. It is also acknowledged that recent initiatives, such as DAFM's iPLAN Scheme*, have the potential to support structured, proactive forest management aimed at increasing forest resilience. However, strengthening the sector's climate resilience will depend on a broader, integrated response, one that addresses underlying policy, economic, and ecological constraints. The following section outlines a range of strategies that could contribute to that goal. While not exhaustive, these proposals are intended to offer practical, evidence-based pathways toward a more sustainable and climate-resilient future for Irish forestry.

Adopt a landscape-level approach

Understanding the spatial and temporal scale at which resilience is integrated into forest systems is critical for strategic forestry planning. While the Forestry Programme 2023–2027 provides grants for a range of forest types, the current afforestation model remains largely reactive and parcel-based, with afforestation decisions driven by landowner applications rather than spatial priorities. Such an approach inherently limits the optimisation of ecosystem services, as shown in recent evidence from England. Burke et al. (2023) found that afforestation planned at the national scale delivered 35% more combined ecosystem service value than parish-level planning and 65% greater benefits than random planting. However, even afforestation targeted at the parish level improved outcomes by c. 30% compared with random planting. A proactive zoning

Figure 4: Summary diagram illustrating the key abiotic, biotic and governance factors impacting forest climate resilience. Mitigation measures are categorised into 1.) Stand scale interventions (black tree) e.g. silvicultural management, fire breaks, deer control, diverse planting to address localised forest management. 2.) National scale interventions (Ireland outline) e.g. investment in research, phytosanitary measure, policy adjustments and streamlined administration to target broader systematic challenges.

strategy would allow land use decisions to be guided by evidence-based assessments of land suitability, supporting the principle of planting “the right trees in the right places for the right reasons” (DAFM 2024c). This approach is corroborated by earlier

work from Farrelly and Gallagher (2015), who identified 3.75 million ha of land suitable for afforestation, of which 2.45 million ha was productive agricultural land and 1.3 million ha marginal land. Furthermore, 341,000 ha of grassland were also noted as having high forestry potential, while current use was limited to summer grazing due to poor trafficability or drainage (ibid).

This zoning-based approach is further supported by the development of the Forestry Opportunities Map (DAFM 2024c), a national GIS tool that overlays data of soils, land cover, environmental designations, water protection zones, and productivity to assess land suitability. The map classifies Ireland's land into five categories (Table 2), ranging from areas suitable for a wide range of forest types to those prioritised for nature conservation or deemed unplantable. In total, 71% of the land area is considered suitable for some form of afforestation, offering a valuable framework for spatial planning.

This map not only supports the identification of afforestation potential but also complements finer-scale studies such as Cullen (2024), who identified c. 88,500 ha of riparian land across Cork, Kerry and Waterford suitable for water quality-focused afforestation (Figure 5). Such targeted assessments could help match specific forest types to particular sites, particularly where environmental sensitivity is high. Equally, a zoning approach using mapping tools could inform decisions relating to existing forests poorly matched to site conditions, for example the c. 24% of the national forest estate located on deep peat soils (DAFM 2022). Identifying such mismatches can help prioritise areas for restoration or alternative management approaches.

Table 2. Land suitability classifications from the Forestry Opportunities Map (DAFM 2024c), including area, percentage of national coverage, and description.

Category	Area (ha)	Percentage of national area	Description
Suitable for a range of forest types	1,809,319	26%	No major environmental constraints; suitable soils for a range of forest types
Suitable for certain forest types	1,784,262	25%	Some environmental sensitivities (e.g. proximity to watercourses); forest type selection may be limited
Suitable for nature conservation and/or amenity forests	1,429,848	20%	Appropriate for non-commercial goals such as biodiversity, amenity or recreation
Unsuitable, unproductive, unplantable	1,227,786	18%	Poor soils or high constraints make afforestation unviable.
Existing forest	776,223	11%	Already under forest cover

Figure 5: In a study about “Opportunity mapping for tree planting as a form of natural flood management in Ireland”. Cullen (2024) derived estimates of land potentially suitable for flood management within the counties Cork, Kerry and Waterford. Left image - **A:** The total “opportunity area” (all catchment area excluding all constraints and sensitivities) identified as suitable for national flood mitigation, i.e. total area available for afforestation 748,171 ha. Right image - **B:** “Priority opportunity area” (focus on poor/very poor draining soils) identified 213,389 ha suitable for flood management. Furthermore, 88,675 ha of land was identified in the riparian zone specifically.

Most importantly, a zoning strategy could streamline afforestation licensing by enabling pre-approved forest types in areas identified as highly suitable, particularly the 1.8 million hectares categorised as “suitable for a range of forest types.” This could significantly reduce application times, lower administrative burden, increase transparency, and improve stakeholder confidence. Region-specific approaches, such as those demonstrated by Cullen (2024), offer a template for expanding zoning from national guidance to regional implementation. This aligns with Duffy et al. (2020), who argue that targeting unprofitable agricultural systems with high afforestation potential can reduce LULUCF emissions while enhancing rural resilience and land-use diversification.

Forests provide a wide array of ecosystem services, including but not limited to, carbon sequestration, timber production, social benefits, biodiversity enhancement, and water quality regulation. However, optimising these services requires careful consideration of spatial and temporal scales (Blattert et al. 2018; Schwaiger et al. 2019; Skytt et al. 2021). The spatial scale of analysis can itself influence the apparent relationships among services, with finer resolutions better suited for detecting localised trade-offs and coarser scales providing a broader policy overview (Roces-Díaz et al. 2018). Crucially, a single forest cannot provide all ecosystem services in equal measures, being limited to subsets of ecosystem services (Lázaro-Lobo et al. 2024). This emphasises the value of regional and national-scale planning over fragmented, site-by-site decision-making. With the average private grant-aided forest size in Ireland being just 8.5 ha (DAFM 2024a), fragmentation inherently limits the potential for delivering multifunctional benefits. While the Forestry Programme requires that 15% of new forest areas be designated as open land for biodiversity, research suggests that separating production and biodiversity objectives across different but complementary areas, rather than trying to combine them within small parcels, can result in more effective ecological and economic outcomes (Blattert et al. 2018). Larger,

strategically located forest blocks, linked by ecological corridors, are more likely to deliver meaningful gains for biodiversity and broader ecosystem service provision.

The development of interactive planning tools using GIS, soil maps, environmental sensitivity layers, and spatial land-use data can play a central role in supporting zoning and targeted grant allocation. Openly accessible tools of this kind would facilitate transparent landowner engagement. To remain effective, such systems must be regularly updated, Farrelly and Gallagher (2015) recommend biennial revisions to spatial datasets to reflect evolving environmental and policy conditions. A pilot project led by DAFM in collaboration with Teagasc forestry advisors, private foresters, and local landowners in a high-potential region could serve as a practical model for national implementation. However, achieving the full potential of a landscape-level, spatially guided approach will require stronger public sector involvement. Since 2003, the responsibility for afforestation has rested largely with private landowners, supported through grant aid. While this has expanded forest cover, it has often prioritised short-term economic returns over long-term ecological resilience. Renewed state participation, particularly in planting forests for water quality, biodiversity and social benefits near national parks and sensitive catchments, could help rebalance objectives and drive progress toward Ireland's EU biodiversity and climate targets (European Commission & Council 2024).

In the context of accelerating climate change and Ireland's legally binding obligations under frameworks such as LULUCF and the Nature Restoration Law, a landscape-level, pre-zoned approach to afforestation represents a transformative opportunity. By combining robust spatial planning, redesigning financial incentives for non-timber benefits such as Nature credits (European Commission 2025) and the emerging carbon removal and carbon farming framework. Ireland can transition towards a more climate-resilient, multifunctional forest estate. This shift is not only vital for the future of the forestry sector, but also foundational to a more integrated and sustainable national land-use strategy.

The role and potential of HWP

Alongside land-use planning, the climate resilience of the forestry sector also depends on sustaining timber markets and maximising the carbon value of HWP. The carbon balance of Irish forestry is significantly influenced by what happens after trees are harvested (Green et al. 2006; Donlan et al. 2012). HWP play a pivotal role in extending carbon storage and reducing emissions beyond the forest boundary.

The importance of HWP as a carbon pool was formally acknowledged under the Kyoto Protocol, with the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) providing guidelines for their inclusion in GHG inventories (IPCC 2006). Timber harvesting transfers carbon from forest ecosystems to HWP, creating a distinct carbon pool that can store carbon over extended periods, contributing to the mitigation of GHG effects

(Gustavsson et al. 2006). The forestry sector supplies a wide range of base products that support diverse downstream industries, including pulp and paper, furniture, and construction. Key products such as lumber, plywood, and by-products like wood chips and sawdust play essential roles in the carbon cycle. The climate mitigation potential of forests is closely tied to the end use of harvested timber biomass, making HWP a pivotal factor in accurately quantifying the overall carbon balance of forests (Lundmark et al. 2016).

HWP mitigate GHG emissions through two primary mechanisms:

1. Carbon storage: carbon absorbed by forests is retained in HWP over their lifespan.
2. Substitution effects: where HWP replace more carbon-intensive materials such as concrete and steel, reduced emissions are associated with these alternatives (Soimakallio et al. 2021).

Recent advances in engineered wood products and timber construction have significantly enhanced the carbon storage potential of HWP. The use of modern technologies, such as Glued Laminated Timber (Glulam) and Cross-Laminated Timber (CLT), has further enhanced the functionality and carbon storage potential of HWP. CLT, for example, is increasingly utilised in multi-storey buildings due to its higher seismic resistance and durability (Wieruszewski & Mazela 2017). These advancements not only increase carbon storage in long-life products but also improve the competitiveness of timber in construction, where it can significantly reduce the carbon footprint of the building process compared to using other conventional materials (Soimakallio et al. 2021).

HWP offer substantial opportunities for reducing emissions in the LULUCF sector. Long-lived products, such as those used in construction and furniture, have the greatest climate mitigation potential. In contrast, short-lived products like paper and bioenergy contribute to net emissions due to their limited lifespan and rapid carbon release (Xue et al. 2024). There is potential for paper-based packaging to offset emissions from plastics, though life cycle assessments (LCA) show variable results. Further optimisation of production processes, greater reuse, and improved end-of-life management are needed to realise this potential (Dolci et al. 2024). Expanding the production and use of long-life HWP is critical for enhancing the carbon storage capacity of forests (Figure 6). Ireland has significant potential to increase the use of HWP through promotion of Irish-grown timber in the architectural and design sector, coupled with stronger public awareness of its climate benefits. Realising this potential depends on sustained innovation and targeted investment in the wood processing sector to scale high-value assortments, improve utilisation of existing resources, and develop durable, low-carbon products (Parobek et al. 2019; DAFM 2025b).

Figure 6: Comparison of total carbon stock over time between unmanaged and sustainably managed Sitka spruce forests. The managed forest considerably outperforms the unmanaged equivalent (dashed black line) in total carbon storage over the 180 period. This demonstrates the combined mitigation potential of sustainable harvesting, product substitution, and bioenergy use. Adapted from Perez-Garcia et al. (2005).

The relationship between HWP and forest disturbance resilience is particularly relevant in an Irish context. Increasing risk from abiotic and biotic threats may reduce the availability of large, high-quality sawlogs, shifting the timber supply towards smaller or lower-grade assortments. However, recent innovations in engineered wood products demonstrate that durable, high-value construction materials can still be produced from such material. For example, Gattas et al. (2024) suggests that controlled lamination techniques have the potential to transform low-value out-of-grade timber into a valuable resource for value-added applications. Furthermore, emerging technologies like densified “superwood” also highlight how wood waste and marginal timber can be converted into products with strength surpassing steel (Song et al. 2018). These innovations highlight the potential to reconcile increased disturbance risks with the climate mitigation role of HWP, provided that adequate investment is made in processing infrastructure and product development.

Despite its advantages, the full climate mitigation potential of HWP remains difficult to quantify. Factors such as end-use efficiency, recycling rates, product lifespan, and potential carbon leakage, where emissions reductions in one jurisdiction result in increased emissions elsewhere, complicate the accounting process (Sikkema et al. 2013; Xue et al. 2024). Comprehensive LCA that integrate spatial, temporal, and product-specific data

are essential for accurately assessing the climate benefits of HWP (Xue et al. 2024). To fully realise the climate mitigation potential of forests, substantial investment in sawmills and the broader wood processing sector is essential. Finally, maintaining a reliable domestic timber supply is critical to unlocking the full value of this renewable resource for Ireland. While native species provide vital ecosystem services, the sustained use of productive non-native species will play a central role in the supply of the raw material needed to maximise the climate benefits offered by HWP.

Promote active, long-term research and knowledge transfer

Effective implementation of climate-resilient forestry strategies depends not only on policy reform and spatial planning but also on a robust, long-term research infrastructure. Addressing knowledge gaps across stand, regional and national scales is essential for building trust among stakeholders, informing adaptive management, and responding to ecological and climatic uncertainty. Key research priorities include climate–species–site matching, elucidating best management on afforested peatlands, modelling growth and yield dynamics in mixed-species stands, quantifying carbon outcomes from different management practices, trialling new species and provenances, forest-assisted migration, and tree breeding for pest and drought resistance. While some short-term projects have explored these topics, fragmented and time-limited funding structures remain a significant barrier to the collection of long-term, high-quality data (Keane et al. 2018).

Establishing test sites offers a pragmatic way to combine strategic research with practical application. An example of this, with particular relevance for Ireland, is Queen Elizabeth Forest Park in Scotland. This park is described as a “climate-ready demonstration forest” and is a pragmatic approach to investigating forest resilience. The park is located in central Scotland and covers an area of c.67,000 ha, of which 54% is forested (Forest Research 2022). The park balances a mixture of management objectives from timber production to tourism, conservation and protective services (slope stability, increasing species and structural diversity). An automated weather station near the site allows researchers to monitor environmental and climatic variables and link them directly to growth, yield and greenhouse gas dynamics (ibid). This park enables potential barriers to the adoption of different management practices at an operational and forest planning level to be identified and addressed. Test sites such as this could prove invaluable as a tool to bolster confidence in alternative management strategies among a diverse range of stakeholders, from the general public, forest owners, forestry practitioners and policy makers. As Vitkova et al. (2013) observed, during the early stages of introducing an alternative management concept, there is often resistance to such change until sufficient evidence and demonstrations are available to convince sceptics of the merits of the new approach.

In the Irish context, long-term monitoring is particularly urgent in areas where emissions dynamics are poorly understood, especially afforested peatlands. Continuous, site-based monitoring of GHG fluxes from these forests is necessary to refine Ireland's carbon accounting under LULUCF and to assess the potential of rewetting or low-impact silvicultural alternatives. Similarly, monitoring of different forest types and management, such as RFM, mixed-species stands, Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF), and agroforestry systems, can generate empirical evidence on resilience, productivity, GHG dynamics and biodiversity outcomes. Without this data, policymakers and forest managers are forced to rely on short-term data, assumptions or extrapolated findings from other regions.

Recent advancements in LiDAR technology and digital twin methodologies (Calders et al. 2020; Savinelli et al. 2024) have significantly enhanced the capacity to monitor and manage forest ecosystems with unprecedented precision and efficiency. For instance, the integration of drone-based LiDAR and multispectral data has proven effective in monitoring tree health and detecting productivity changes within forests (Savinelli et al. 2024). The "digital twin" concept further enables the quantification of disturbances, growth, yield and carbon dynamics at resolutions and accuracies not previously possible (Silva et al. 2023). These technologies can greatly enhance our ability to assess management scenarios, predict climate impacts, and support decision-making under uncertainty.

Together, these research and monitoring tools can fill critical evidence gaps and support an evidence-based transition toward a more climate-smart and resilient forest estate. Establishing long-term experimental forests and investing in national-scale monitoring systems would be invaluable for overcoming resistance, refining strategy, and unlocking the full potential of Irish forestry in climate mitigation and adaptation. Equally important is the transfer of this knowledge through education and extension programmes for landowners and practitioners. Recent evidence highlights that well-designed initiatives, such as thinning demonstrations, can significantly improve both learning and management outcomes among new private forest owners, a group often lacking in management experience (Upton et al. 2019). Strengthening extension services and embedding educational programmes within the forestry sector for landowners and forestry practitioners alike will be crucial for ensuring that scientific advancements are translated into practice on the ground.

Conclusion

Accelerated climate change represents one of the most pressing challenges facing land-use systems globally. Understanding its extent, pace, and variability is critical to developing a climate-resilient forest estate and ensuring its long-term sustainability. The historical reliance on Sitka spruce within Irish forestry is understandable, its high productivity, timber yield, carbon sequestration capacity, and tolerance of marginal sites have made it a key stone species. However, this singular focus also introduces systemic risks: reduced ecological

adaptability, vulnerability to disturbance, with implications for rural communities, carbon storage, and the wider forest sector. While Sitka spruce will undoubtedly remain a cornerstone of Irish forestry, contributing significantly to timber production, supply of HWP and carbon sequestration (DAFM 2022), its dominance must be balanced with the cultivation of a diverse mosaic of forest types. These should be designed to optimise ecosystem service provision on a national scale, including biodiversity conservation, water quality protection, and social benefits, alongside timber production. Greater variation in silvicultural approaches will be needed to meet evolving management objectives and to support the integration of forestry with other land uses, such as agriculture, wetland restoration, and climate mitigation.

Proactively addressing the predicted future impacts of climate change will be vital to ensuring the resilience and sustainability of Irish forests. Achieving this will require transformative change underpinned by cross-sectoral collaboration, engaging stakeholders from forestry, agriculture, biodiversity, research, governance as well as landowners. Such collaboration must support a transition in both policy and practice, grounded in adaptive management, landscape-level planning, and sustained investment in research, innovation, and monitoring.

Building climate resilience in the Irish forest estate will require a multi-faceted, forward-looking approach. This includes rethinking conventional practices, embracing innovation, and tailoring strategies across spatial and temporal scales.

In summary, three key shifts are needed:

1. Develop long-term forest research infrastructure including research stations, permanent experimental forests, and skilled human resources.
2. Adopt climate-smart forestry practices such as diversification of species and adaptive silvicultural management, informed by the research base.
3. Align policy with research and practice ensuring progress from (1) and (2) is supported, while also removing unnecessary administrative barriers.

Without these changes, the Irish forestry sector will remain exposed to growing climate, ecological and social pressures, undermining its functionality and contribution to national and EU climate goals.

“In times of rapid change, experience could be your worst enemy.” - J. Paul Getty.

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